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INTRODUCTION

It is well known that economic reforms are an important factor in the development of society. The Action Strategy pays special attention to this issue and identifies economic development and liberalization as the third priority. In particular, to further strengthen macroeconomic stability and maintain high economic growth rates. For example, for the past 26 years, Uzbekistan has not kept its GDP below 8%. It is one of the top five fastest growing countries in the world. Further development of this historic achievement and preservation of the status of an economically powerful state is the main content of the Action Strategy.

Econometric methods do not negate simple traditional methods, but help to further develop them and to analyze the objective variable outcome indicators through other indicators. One of the advantages of econometric methods and

THE ROLE OF ECONOMIC ANALYSIS IN ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

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ABSTRACT

Econometric knowledge is distinguished and formed as a result of the interdependence and development of disciplines such as economic theory, economic mathematics, economic statistics, probability theory, and mathematical statistics. Econometrics shapes its subject, purpose, and research. At the same time, the content of econometrics, its composition and scope are in constant contact with the above disciplines.

computers in the management of the national economy is that they can be used to show the impact of factors on the modeling object, the relationship of resources to the resultant indicator. This allows for the scientific forecasting and management of production results and the national economy in dozens of industries and thousands of enterprises. Econometric modeling defines the laws of change of economic indicators, ways to develop and forecast economic processes using econometric models as a result of identifying trends. Economic data is organized in the form of a dynamic series or dynamic column, that is, they change over time. The number of observations should be 4-5 times the number of factors.

The importance of econometric modeling and models can be seen in:

1) Material, labor and monetary resources are used rationally using econometric methods.

2) Econometric methods and models serve as a leading tool in the development of economics and natural sciences.

3) It will be possible to make some adjustments during the overall implementation of forecasts made using econometric methods and models.

4) With the help of econometric models, it is possible not only to analyze economic processes in depth, but also to discover their new unexplored laws. They can also be used to predict the future development of the economy.

5) Econometric methods and models, along with the automation of computational work, facilitate mental labor, organize and manage the work of employees of the economic sphere on a scientific basis.

The main econometric methods are mathematical statistical methods and econometric methods. Methods of mathematical statistics - variance analysis, correlation analysis, regression analysis, factor analysis, index theory. Econometric methods - the theory of economic growth, the theory of production functions, the theory of supply and demand. The process of studying econometrics is the process of creating econometric models of economic processes.

The main method used is the correlation-regression analysis method. Econometric modeling is a complex of scientific directions: - economic theory; - probability theory; - mathematical statistics; - computer technology

Macroeconomic processes cover all sectors of the national economy. Macroeconomic processes basically study and explain three major processes. These are:

1 Unemployment.

2 Inflation.

3 Economic growth.

Unemployment is defined as the inactivity of an active, able-bodied population in a country.

Inflation is the growth of general prices in a country.

Economic growth means that the country's population is producing more and more gross domestic product each year.

These three indicators are macroeconomic problems.

The above problems arise due to the unsustainable development of the economy. There are several ways to solve these problems. These problems can arise from a variety of conditions, such as government economic policies, fiscal and monetary policies.

The expanded reproduction model, which is formed at the level of the national economy, serves to determine the rate of growth and 'rotations'.

One-sector and two-sector models of economic growth can be considered.

$X(t)$ is the national income produced in a year;

$Y(t)$ - went to the growth of fixed assets in the non-manufacturing sector

expenditures and the share of national income consumed;

$J(t)$ - capital investment in the growth of fixed assets;

$S(t)$ is the rate (contribution) of capital investment in net production.

Given this economic context, the following expression can be written:

$$X(t) = Y(t) + J(t)$$

And the standard of the fund

$$S(t) = J(t) / X(t)$$

determined by the formula

There is an inextricable link between the size of the fund and the rate of economic growth. The parameter $V(t)$ is defined to represent this relationship. It characterizes the ratio between the current growth of national income and the sum of net capital investments in fixed assets (ie, the level of return on capital expenditures):

$$U(t) = (X(t+1) - X(t)) / Y(t) = \Delta X(t) / Y(t)$$

$$Y(t) = S(t) \cdot X(t)$$

Because

$$U(t) = \Delta X(t) / S(t) \cdot X(t); \Delta X(t) / X(t) = S(t) \cdot U(t) \text{ ega bo'lamiz.}$$

Consequently, the growth rate of national income represents a form of savings economic growth of capital expenditures. If the savings rate and the capital investment estimate are independent parameters of economic growth and increase (decrease), the savings rate is equal to the proportional increase (decrease) of national income growth rates under other equal conditions. will pass. Assuming a constant level of efficiency of the capital spent, we obtain the Harrod-Domar model of economic growth.

$$X(t) = Y(t) + J(t)$$

$$\Delta K(t) = J(t)$$

$$J(t) = S \cdot X(t)$$

$$X(t) = q \cdot K(t)$$

In this case, $K(t)$ determines the size of fixed assets in the economy. q is the efficiency ratio of funds $q = X / K$. In the absence of a "delay" in this model, the equation for the long-term rate of economic growth can be derived:

$$\lambda = \Delta X(t) / X(t) = q \cdot S$$

Conclusions

Economic growth is the foundation of a nation's well-being. Analyzing the interrelationships between economic growth and the factors that affect it, and

using mathematical models and methods in the process, gives good results.

In solving this problem, we have considered the production functions of the linear programming course of mathematics, the constant elastic interaction of production factors of Cobb-Douglas, Arrow-Cheneri and others, and Bruno's methods of using fixed quantities in production. .

Determining the absolute and relative growth rates and elasticity coefficients of the economy.

The practical application of the above enterprise development and deployment models will depend on the network being modeled, the types of products produced, the resources used, and a number of other factors. Placement and development models of enterprises producing the same type of product. Any economic entity can be affected by various changes during its life; expansion, re-equipment, reduction of production, etc. At the same time, the current planning problems include the full use of the existing production capacity of the enterprise, the adaptation of the composition of products to market demand and the determination of the volume of production. The problems of creating new capacity, modifying existing ones, and expanding them will be solved through long-term planning methods.

The placement and development models of many types of manufacturing enterprises determine the volume of production of the link, in addition to the newly built and re-equipped enterprises in the industry. It involves the production of a variety of products. These products can be produced

together with the main products of the enterprise.

REFERENCES:

1. Econometrics. Uchebnik. / pod red. prof. I.I.Eliseevoy. -M .: Finance and Statistics, 2004.
2. Zaxarchenko A.I. Business statistics and forecasting in MS Excel. -M .: Izd. dom. Williams, 2004.
3. Gorbunov VK Matematicheskaya model potrebitelskogo sprosa.Teoriya i prikladnoy potentsial. M .: Economics, 2004.-174p.
4. Mukhamadqodirovich R. A. The role of mass media in the history of the period of independence // ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal. - 2020. - T. 10. - №. 4. - S. 356-359.